
Analysis of Development in Sugarcane Cultivation: A Case Study of Kolhapur District

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063270

Abstract:

Kolhapur district, renowned for its fertile soil and favorable climatic conditions, has long been a significant sugarcane-producing region in Maharashtra, India. The district of Kolhapur has registered significant success in the cultivation of commercial crops such as an assortment of cereals, fruits, and vegetables. Over the years, the sugarcane cultivation landscape in Kolhapur has undergone significant changes, driven by various factors such as technological advancements, changing market dynamics, and government policies. Present study examines development of area under sugarcane cultivation from 2013 to 2023. Comparative analysis method is used for this research paper. As well as ArcGIS and MS Excell software is used for investigation of changes in past decade. Both sugarcane area and production have increased during the period 2013 to 2023 in Kolhapur district. Almost 16% area increased under sugarcane cultivation in Kolhapur district. The development in Gadhinglaj tehsil are rapidly change from past decade.

Keyword: Sugarcane, Cultivation area, Development, Commercial Crop.

Introduction:

In the entire state of Maharashtra, not only in the Kolhapur region, sugarcane is a significant commercial crop. Agriculturists, mill owners, and the federal and state governments all have a significant role in the crop. In addition to giving farmers a source of income, sugarcane production supplies sugarcane mills with essential raw ingredients. The majority of farmers cultivate sugarcane for this reason. But when they are cultivated, some other crops, such as maize, wheat, cotton, jowar, and bajri, provide farmers with a good income. In Kolhapur district, however, the area planted to sugarcane has grown, but the area planted to other crops has declined.

The district of Kolhapur has registered significant success in the cultivation of commercial crops such as an assortment of cereals, fruits, and vegetables. However, it is sugarcane that has made the region quite distinct, with acres and acres of fertile fields bustling with sugarcane cultivation. This pulse-quicken region along the western coast of India has particularly earned a distinction with regular bumper crops of sugarcane. Therefore, it is the sugarcane industry that occupies pride of place in all economic and financial transactions of Kolhapur district. The Maharashtra State Co-operative Banks in Kolhapur, Kolhapur District Industries Centre, and the Maharashtra State Finance Corporation are engaged in providing loans

on a large scale to the sugarcane cultivators and factories. Public and private financial firms, especially the State Bank of India, are other active partners.

Its cultivation involves a number of farm operations and intensive labor. A study of sugarcane cultivation in Kolhapur district provides a fascinating insight into an economic activity that has assumed considerable importance as the main source of wealth of the region. The climatic and geographical conditions of the area are very suitable for sugarcane cultivation. The more or less uniform distribution of rain over most of the year, as well as the fertile black soils of the region, have been a particular attraction. These soil and weather conditions, in combination with a variety of factors, have turned sugarcane into the main crop of the district. With nearly 178,107 hectares of land under sugarcane cultivation in the district, it has beaten other commercial crops such as groundnut and soybean. During the crushing season, the number of these workers escalates into the thousands, though the active workers among them cannot be more than half of the total.

The present paper constitutes an attempt to study the changes in sugarcane cultivation and to understand the existing conditions of this crop.

Objective:

1. To analyze development in sugarcane cultivation area of Kolhapur district.

Literature Review:

Sugarcane is an important commercial crop in India, playing a pivotal role in the country's agricultural and industrial economy (Kumar et al., 2019). In 2013-14, sugarcane accounted for 6% of the overall value of agriculture output and

covered 2.5% of India's gross cropped area. (Sherpa et al., 2017) India ranks second among the sugarcane growing countries of the world in both area and production after Brazil, with an area under sugarcane cultivation of 4.94 million hectares and an average yield of 68.6 tons per hectare (Verma & Solanki, 2020). The sugar industry in India is the second largest agro-industry, second only to the textile industry, and it plays a vital role in developing the socioeconomic status in rural areas by making use of its resources and generating employment. (Sherpa et al., 2017) Sugarcane is grown mainly for the manufacture of sugar, as well as for making gur and khandasari. (Vijayakumar et al., 2020)

Study Area:

Kolhapur district is selected as the study region for the proposed research work. The region lies between 15° 45" and 17° 10" North latitudes, and between 73° 40" and 74° 42" East longitudes. It covers an area of 7685 sq. kms, which is 2.49 % of total area of the state. The Krishna, Panchaganga, Dudhganga, Vedganga, Warna, Hiranyakeshi, Ghatprabha etc. are the major rivers with their tributaries influencing on agriculture of the study region. In 2011 population of the region is 3876001 which are 3.44 % of the total population of the state. The region includes 12 revenue and 1216 Villages. Shahuwadi tehsil has 145 villages, Panhala 129, Hatkanangale 58, Shirol 54, Karvir 121, Gaganbawada 45, Radhanagari 114, Kagal 84 Ajra 99, Gadhinglaj 93, Chandgad 157, and Bhudargad 117. In Kolhapur district 68.26 per cent of population live in rural area. The region is bounded on the north by Sangli district, on the west by Ratnagiri and Sidhudhurg district, on the south and east by Belgaum district of Karnataka states.

Figure 1: Location Map of Study Area

Data & Methodology:

Secondary data is used for this particular research study. Specifically Socio-Economic Abstract of Kolhapur District is used. Also to analyze the changes in sugarcane cultivation in Kolhapur district, a comprehensive review of secondary data from various sources was conducted. Year 2013 and 2023 are used for analyzing difference. For the analysis and mapping ArcGIS software is used.

Result & Discussion:

1. Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2013:

Table 1: Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2013

Sr. No.	Taluka	Total Cultivated Area	Sugarcane Cultivated Area	Percentage (%)
1	Shahuwadi	56007	4130	7.374
2	Panhala	33672	10280	30.52
3	Hathkanangle	60005	20400	33.99
4	Shirol	48631	22800	46.88
5	Karvir	63369	21709	34.25
6	Gaganbawda	31545	3360	10.65
7	Radhanagari	38824	8791	22.64
8	Kagal	54555	20634	37.82
9	Bhudargad	35322	5490	15.54
10	Ajara	46353	4700	10.13
11	Gadhinglaj	47671	10021	21.02
12	Chandgad	59622	12971	21.75
	Total	575576	145286	25.24

Figure 2: Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2013

Table 1 and figure 2 are showing tehsil wise percentage of area under sugarcane cultivation to total area of crop cultivation in year 2013. As we see Hatkanangale, Shirol, Karvir and Kagal tehsil have maximum share of cultivated area under sugarcane cultivation and Shahuwadi, Gaganbawada as well as Ajara tehsil have minimum share of cultivated area under sugarcane cultivation.

2. Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2023:

Table 2 : Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2013

Sr. No.	Taluka	Total Cultivated Area	Sugarcane Cultivated Area	Percentage (%)
1	Shahuwadi	26716	7504	28.08
2	Panhala	34864	14210	40.75
3	Hathkanangle	55755	23694	42.49
4	Shirol	34528	27967	80.99
5	Karvir	40557	24060	59.32
6	Gaganbawda	6590	3832	58.14
7	Radhanagari	29371	12915	43.97
8	Kagal	49693	25766	51.85
9	Bhudargad	30083	7140	23.73
10	Ajara	25821	4920	19.05
11	Gadhinglaj	42017	10052	23.92
12	Chandgad	51020	13500	26.46
	Total	427015	175560	41.11

Table 2 and figure 3 are showing tehsil wise percentage of area under sugarcane cultivation to total area of crop cultivation in year 2023. As we see Shirol, Karvir, Gaganbawada and Kagal tehsil have

maximum share of cultivated area under sugarcane cultivation and Shahuwadi, Bhudargad, Ajara, Gadhinglaj as well as Chandgad tehsil have minimum share of cultivated area under sugarcane cultivation.

Figure 3: Cultivated Area Under Sugarcane Crop 2023

3. Total Area under Sugarcane Cultivation:

As we see in figure number 4, the total area under sugarcane cultivation in year 2013 is 145286 hectares and total area under sugarcane cultivation in year 2023 is 175560 hectares which means the area under cultivated of sugarcane is increased in last decade.

Adoption of High-Yielding Varieties (HYVs) (HYVs like Co 86032 and CoM 0265 has significantly boosted sugarcane productivity in the region), Mechanization of Agricultural Practices (the

adoption of modern farm machinery, such as tractors, harvesters, and threshers, has increased efficiency and reduced labor costs. Mechanization has also helped in timely sowing, harvesting, and post-harvest operations.), Improved Irrigation Systems(The development of irrigation infrastructure, including canals, dams, and tube wells, has ensured a reliable water supply for sugarcane cultivation), Fertilizer and Pesticide Management (adopting soil testing and nutrient management practices), Government Support and Policies (Government subsidies, crop insurance

schemes, and credit facilities have provided financial support), Shift Towards Value-Added Products (value-added sugarcane

products like jaggery, molasses, and ethanol to enhance their income)

Figure 4: Total Area Under Sugarcane Cultivation

Comparison of Cultivated Area under Sugarcane Crop between Year 2013& 2023:

The data shows that the area under sugarcane cultivation in Kolhapur district has steadily increased over the past decade. In 2013 area under sugarcane cultivation was low in Shahuwadi, Gaganbawada, Bhudargad, Aajara and Gadhinglaj tehsil. Medium area under sugarcane cultivation were Panhala, Radhanagari and Chandgad tehsil. As well as high under cultivation area of sugarcane were Karvir, Kagal, Hatkanangale and Shirol tehsil.

In 2023 area under sugarcane cultivation was low in in Shahuwadi, Gaganbawada, Bhudargad and Aajara tehsil. Medium area under sugarcane cultivation were Panhala, Radhanagari, Gadhinglaj and

Chandgad tehsil. As well as high under cultivation area of sugarcane were Karvir, Kagal, Hatkanangale and Shirol tehsil.

If we compare both of them we can conclude that the development in Gadhinglaj tehsil are rapidly change from past decade. Shirol Tehsil has highest area under sugarcane cultivation. Due to the introduction of high yielding, early maturity, diseases and pest resistant variety and recommendation of wider row spacing, use of trash mulch and adopting the recommended packages of practices regarding the sugarcane cultivation helped in improving farmer’s sugarcane yield. The yield level of farmers from last decades has substantially increased by adopting the new technology, ultimately resulted in increased the farmer income.

Figure 5 &6 Area Under Sugarcane Cultivation in 2013 and 2023

Conclusion:

Sugarcane crop plays vital role in agriculture of Kolhapur. Area under cultivated sugarcane crop increasing rapidly as compare to another crops. Good climate, heavy rainfall, availability of water, good structure of soil, availability of labors, availability of sugar factories as well as technological progress are the main reasons behind it. Also farmers have increasingly adopted high-yielding varieties like Co 92005, which is well-suited to the region's climate and soil conditions.

Government policies and subsidies have played a crucial role in shaping sugarcane cultivation practices. Fluctuations in sugarcane prices can impact farmers' decisions regarding cultivation and harvesting. Modern agricultural techniques, such as drip irrigation and use of fertilizers, have enhanced sugarcane productivity. Mechanization of sugarcane cultivation has reduced labor costs and increased efficiency. The demand for sugar and sugarcane byproducts, such as ethanol and bagasse, influences cultivation decisions. International market trends, including sugar prices and trade policies, can impact the sugarcane industry in Kolhapur.

Conflict of Interest:

There are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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